

MANAGEMENT SKILLS AND SCHOOL HEADS' PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. The study determined the extent of management skills and the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public secondary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of management skills was extensive while the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the management skills have a strong positive correlation to the school heads performance of public secondary schools. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed that the following have a strong influence of management skills on school heads performance of public secondary schools: Leadership, Communication, and Organization. It was suggested that the Department of Education should develop a training/enhancement program that would develop the management skills of secondary school principals as they are school and community leaders in the 21st century. It was also recommended that the school heads should upgrade their management skills among secondary school heads should be continuously enhanced through attending seminars, training, and graduate studies as well as postgraduate courses.

KEY WORDS

1. Management skills 2. school heads performance 3. leadership

1. Introduction

The success of a school critically depends on the school heads who are responsible for ensuring that all teachers and students meet challenging tasks and the desired standard level in education. Nowadays, school heads are empowered to initiate programs and projects that would lead to the improvement of instruction, and as such, they are directly and solely accountable to the appointing authority. School heads are given wide latitude to decide on how to improve their schools. Management is essential to ensure the coordination of individual efforts.

Managerial skills are essential capabilities that determine the effectiveness of an executive or head of an organization, including in a school. It is viewed as the ability to plan, organize, and direct the operations of an educational enterprise for the educational system. Managerial skills are essential in any organization. They establish the conditions and expectations for excellent instruction and the development of a learning culture for both educators and students. Management abilities are essential for successful and efficient planning, staffing, organizing,

coordinating, managing, and decision-making.

Therefore, managerial skills are the ability, knowledge, and experience necessary to execute management responsibilities and achieve organizational objectives and goals. Principals are under tremendous pressure to demonstrate the importance of their work to the progress of the school. As a result, decision-making is at the heart of management, and it strives to choose the optimal option for achieving a goal. School heads play a critical role in helping the school by articulating a common purpose and establishing distributed leadership within a collaborative school climate. Principals display leadership through tools and procedures, and situational decision-making requires them to make their own choices. The law precisely defines how the school principal has to carry out his responsibilities, and it is expected that one's leadership qualities would be put to the best possible advantage. Organizational success is dependent on effective leadership. Behavior is often recognized as one of the most influential variables in leadership. A school organization, like any other organization, needs strong leadership and management. Both set the direction for the school organization to follow. The application of different management and leadership principles and practices in a school setting complement each other. School leadership and management activities challenge everyone in the field to promote the culture of lifelong learning and teaching.

Globally, management is one of the most important human activities. In modern times, the concept of management has become crucial and challenging for managers in dealing with complex organizations. Decision-making is considered critically as a key factor in the development and performance of an organization (Islam, 2018).

Managers at all levels shape the organizational values and culture through their decisions and by setting an example. The organizational performance is the best evidence of the man-

agers' efforts through their competence and skills in managing people to achieve the organizational goals and objectives. Managers are responsible for efficiently completing activities with and through other people and for setting and achieving the organizational goals through the execution of four basic management functions: planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. Both sets of processes utilize human, financial, and material resources (Dar, 2017).

According to Olum (2018), management requires core skills based on modern management theories and practices, such as technical skills, which involve knowledge and proficiency in activities, methods, processes, and procedures. To be effective, particularly at upper organizational levels, managers must be able to do more than just identify problems. They must also have the valuable skill of being able to design workable solutions to the problems in light of the realities they face.

Sindhvad's (2019) study on school heads' capacity as instructional leaders found that in Asia, many school principals were not prepared for their new role and function in school management. Managers do things right, but leaders do the right things. Additionally, the principal's role has been altered by the advent of school or site-based management, which has led to the decentralization of control, transferring considerable decision-making from the district office to individual schools to give principals, teachers, and others more authority over what happens in schools (Wohlstette, 2018). All of these make the roles that building principals face every day more complex than ever.

Today's school heads also have a heavy workload and work at a rapid pace that is both hectic and taxing. On average, elementary school heads work fifty-one hours a week, and high school principals average about fifty-three hours a week (Lunenburg, 2017). Increasingly, school heads are also being pushed (not so gently) into instructional and community leadership

roles. According to Mendels (2018), today's school heads need to focus on instruction and not building management.

Similarly, in the Philippines, school heads display management by tools and procedures, and situational decision-making requires them to make their own choices. To effectively lead schools toward achieving educational goals, school principals must have a wide range of skills that lead to changing expectations of what leaders must know and do (Victor, 2017). In the study of Aquino (2020), it is stressed that the management of a school is a complex function that requires sophistication in practice.

Zulieta et al. (2017) as cited by Magsayo (2021) further support the findings that effective school heads need various skills that range from technical design. School heads must have the will to implement the solutions they come up with and must recognize the emotions, needs, and motivations of people involved in initiating the necessary change, as well as those who resist change. Additionally, the results revealed that school leaders' managerial skills were rated as "always," indicating that school leaders demonstrated effective managerial skills, as assessed by the teachers. The study also disclosed a significant correlation between the managerial skills of school leaders and teachers' perfor-

mance.

Managerial skills are essential in any organization. It establishes the conditions and expectations for excellent instruction and the developing learning culture for both educators and learners. For decades, educational officials worldwide have pushed to enhance school performance (Abdurahman Omar, 2021). For school managers, the primary consequence of this shift in policy has been competent managers who guide the organization in attaining the school's objective, which is largely focused on education and development, is a critical component of a successful school. The schools would be successful, and the teachers' performance would improve as a catalyst for change if the school heads had the necessary administrative abilities. Therefore, the researchers are motivated to investigate the managerial skills of school heads and teachers' performance in selected schools.

Management oversees achieving a specific aim or target represented through goals or objectives. In addition, there must be a good way for people to communicate with each other. There must be a good communication mechanism between teachers, students, and school officials both inside and outside the school to fulfill the goals of all levels.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures. In preparing this paper, the researcher used artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was used to improve the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This is explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The use of AI for proofreading demonstrates a commitment to responsibly leveraging advanced technologies and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. Accord-

ing to San Gaspar (2017), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to as-

certain their relationship. More to the point, Swart (2018) emphasizes that this method used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses the management skills of public secondary schools of North District, Division of Tagum City. This is correlational since management skills and school heads performance of public secondary schools.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in four (4) schools of North District, Division of Tagum City. The respondents were composed of 120-selected teachers of North District, Division of Tagum City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the management skills and school heads performance of public secondary school. Random sampling technique was employed in this study. However, Tagum City National Comprehensive High School, Laureta National High School, and La Filipina National High School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools were equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used an adapted questionnaire on management skills. It was patterned and adapted by the researcher from the Total Quality Management Theory of Deming (1993) as cited by Magsayo (2021) which states that the dealt on the complex duties and responsibilities of school heads espoused with difficulties in dealing with different internal and external forces in the work-

place. He asserted that that focused on improving quality would automatically reduce costs while those that focused on reducing cost would automatically reduce quality and increase costs as a result. Deming's system of profound knowledge pronounces that the prevailing style of management must undergo transformation. This was supported by DepEd Order No. 02, s. 2021 on the Electronic Contextualized RPMS Tool (OPCRF). The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher's preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Tagum City. Validity of the instrument ensured through expert's opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach's Alpha with the obtained values of 0.070. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, namely components management skills and school heads performance of public secondary schools of North District, Division of Tagum City. Hence, the Cronbach's value of the construct had met the minimum reliability of 0.796, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument's face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items management skills with the following: leadership, planning and strategy, communication, and organization. Part 2 pertained to the school heads performance namely: operation function, learning environment, human resource management and development and parents' involvement and community partnership.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The steps followed in the conduct of the study were:

1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from

Range Descriptive Equivalents and Interpretations for Management Skills

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The management skills are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The management skills are oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The management skills are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The management skills are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The management skills are not evident.

Range Descriptive Equivalents and Interpretations for School Head's Performance

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The school heads performance is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The school heads performance is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The school heads performance is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The school heads performance is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The school heads performance is not evident.

the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Tagum City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher's email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time;

therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2020. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean. It was used to determine the extent of management skills of public secondary schools in North District, Division of Tagum City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining

the significant of management skills and school heads performance of public secondary schools in North District, Division of Tagum City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant of management skills influence school heads performance of public secondary schools' teachers of North District, Division of Tagum City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of management skills and school heads of public secondary schools of North District, Division of Tagum City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of management skills in terms of leadership, planning and strategy, communication, and organization; the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools in terms of operation function, learning environment, human resource management and development; and which of the factors of management skills significantly influence the school heads performance of public secondary schools of North District, Division of Tagum City.

Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the extent of management skills of public secondary schools of North District, Division of

Tagum City. The indicator with highest mean is leadership with a mean of (3.98), interpreted as extensive. Then, it is followed by organization

has a mean of (3.85) identified as extensive. In addition, planning and strategy acknowledged a mean of (3.67) which also identified as extensive. Lastly, communication has the least mean of (3.57) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.77) or extensive, therefore, the summary on the extent of management skills of public secondary schools was extensive as perceived by the school heads. This means that school heads had high commitment in terms of leading and managing the

schools. Majority of the school heads are responsible for the effective general management of the school, for ensuring the provision of academic leadership and strategic vision, and for the quality of the learner experience. In school organization, school heads are leaders who are responsible for the survival of the organization, for managing operation and administration of schools, mentoring education personnel, and efficiently utilizing and maintaining facilities and infrastructure.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Management Skills

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Leadership	3.98	Extensive
2	Planning and Strategy	3.67	Extensive
3	Communication	3.57	Extensive
4	Organization	3.85	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.77	Extensive

Presented in table 2 shows the summary on the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools. The indicator with highest mean is parents' involvement and community partnership (4.22), interpreted as very extensive. It is then followed by operation function has a mean of (4.04) identified as extensive. Similarly, human resource management and de-

velopment obtained a mean of (3.90) described as extensive. Lastly, learning environment has the least mean of (3.85) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (4.00) or extensive, therefore, the summary on the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools was extensive as perceived by the school heads. This means that family-

school-community partnerships promote family and community involvement in children's schooling, with school encouraging parental as-

sistance with homework, providing leadership opportunities, forming partnerships with local organizations, and more.

Shown on Table 3 is correlational analysis on the significant relationship management skills and school heads performance. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.774. This means that there is a strong significant positive correlation

between management skills and school heads performance. Hence, this study rejects its set null hypothesis. Relatively, the analysis shows that an increasing manifestations of management skills leads to an increased performance of school heads of public secondary schools.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of School Heads Performance

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Operation Function	4.04	Extensive
2	Learning Environment	3.85	Extensive
3	Human Resource Management and Development	3.90	Extensive
4	Parents Involvement and Community Partnership	4.22	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.00	Extensive

Specifically, the analysis in table 3 highlighted the relationship between each indicator of the management skills with the school heads performance variable of the study. Based on the analysis, the Leadership indicator ranked as the top indicator of management skills with a significant strong positive correlation to school heads performance obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.689. This was followed by the Organization indicator with still a significant strong positive correlation to school heads performance obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.658. Third, is the Planning Strat-

egy indicator a significant moderate positive correlation to school heads performance obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.534. Lastly, the Communication indicator a significant moderate positive correlation to school heads performance obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.419. Consecutively, all of the indicators of management skills show positive direct relationship to school heads performance. This means that as the indicators of management skills were increasingly manifesting, then performance of school heads will also tend to increase.

As shown in the Table 4, the overall analysis using the Multiple Linear Regression statistical treatment obtained p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 51.100 stating that there is a significant influence of management skills on the school heads performance. This implies that the regres-

sion model used in the analysis of the study is useful and that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influence of management skills. Out of the four indicators of management skills in this study, three (3) of them significantly influenced the school heads

Table 3. Management Skills Correlation and Hypothesis Testing

Management Skills	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Leadership	0.689	0.000	Reject
Planning & Strategy	0.534	0.000	Reject
Communication	0.419	0.000	Reject
Organization	0.658	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.774	0.000	Reject

performance. The said indicators were the Leadership indicator obtaining a t-value of 6.855 and p-value of 0.000, the Organization indicator obtaining a t-value of 4.297 and p-value of 0.000, and the Communication indicator obtaining a t-value of 2.273 and p-value of 0.025.

Table 4. School Heads Performance: Regression Analysis

Management Skills	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Hypothesis Testing		
	B		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho
Constant	1.045					4.668	0.000	
Leadership	0.325		0.450	0.047	6.855		0.000	Reject
Planning & Strategy	0.089		0.117	0.055	1.631		0.106	Accept
Communication	0.129		0.145	0.057	2.273		0.025	Reject
Organization	0.228		0.314	0.053	4.297		0.000	Reject

Relatively, these three indicators were established in the results of the regression analysis where R² is equal to 0.640. This means that there are 64 percent ascribed to the significant influence of management skills on the school heads performance. Thus, the other 36 percent is ascribed to the other indicators not stipulated in the study. Particularly, these said indicators could be included to determine that they might have stipulated influence to the school heads performance. With this finding, the set null

hypothesis of this study that there are no indicators of management skills that significantly influence school heads performance is rejected. On the other hand, the Planning and Strategy indicator of management skills variable obtained a t-value of 1.631 and p-value of 0.106. This indicator failed to reject the null hypothesis of the study. Hence, this indicator as part of the management skills variable in this study is considered not significant.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of management skills and the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools. Specifi-

cally, this study aimed to determine the extent of management skills in terms of leadership, planning and strategy, communication, and organization. Moreover, this identified the extent of school heads performance of public sec-

ondary schools in terms of operation function, learning environment, human resource management and development, and parents' involvement and community partnership. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of management skills and the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools. Using the non-experimental research, the extent of management skills and school heads performance of public secondary schools was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public secondary school teachers in North District, Division of Tagum City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Deming (2006) as cited by Magsayo (2021) and was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the level of management skills in terms of leadership, planning and strategy, communication, and organization was extensive. Similarly, the extent of school heads performance of public secondary schools in terms of operation function, learning environment, human resource management and development, and parents' involvement and community partnership was extensive which means that it was sometimes manifested while in terms of management skills which also extensive. Hence, the extent of school heads performance as demonstrated by public secondary schools of North District, Division of Tagum City was extensive. Finally, indicators of management skills such as leadership, communication, and organization have significant influence of school heads performance of public secondary schools.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The management of public secondary school heads skills was extensive. The school heads performance of public secondary schools was also extensive. There was a strong positive correlation between management skills and school heads performance of public secondary schools based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of management skills to the school heads performance of public secondary schools: leadership, communication, and organization.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: The Department of Education (DepEd) should develop a training/seminars and enhancement programs that would develop the management skills of the school heads as they are school and community leaders in the 21st century. School heads conduct seminars and workshops on Different and Management Style to sustain high performance in managing and leading the school. School heads should manage change and develop a mechanism to improve the school's system through creative support of its own manpower of teachers, staff, learners and community. Education can be effective in an environment which is not conducive for teaching and learning. Future Researchers may use the findings of this as springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore other dimension of the study.

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